

SOCIAL ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF COOPERATION “FAMILY – NEIGHBORHOOD – EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION”

Karimova Gulnoza

lecturer, Fergana State University,

Salieva Nigora

lecturer, Fergana Medical Institute of Public Health,

Uzbekistan, Fergana city

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Abstract: as you know, a person first grows and grows in the family, forms as a person. Family upbringing, spiritual and moral values will later find their place among people, that is, in the neighborhood, in the family, in educational institutions. Therefore, it is impossible to resolve the day of tomorrow of our motherland and people, the grandiose like the coming of age of the perfect generation, which determines the prestige of the world community, without the cooperation of a family-neighborhood-educational institution.

In this article, the social aspects of the development of cooperation "family-neighborhood-educational institution" were studied.

Keywords: society, family, neighborhood, school, social protection, social activities, personality education, healthy generation, civil society.

СОЦИАЛЬНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ РАЗВИТИЯ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА «СЕМЬЯ – МИКРОРАЙОН – ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЕ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЕ»

Аннотация: как известно, человек сначала растет и воспитывается в семье, формируется как личность. Семейное воспитание, духовные и нравственные ценности позже найдут свое место среди людей, то есть по соседству, в семье, в образовательных учреждениях. Поэтому невозможно решить завтрашний день нашей родины и народа, такой грандиозный, как совершеннолетие совершенного поколения, определяющего престиж мирового сообщества, без сотрудничества семьи-соседства-образовательного учреждения.

В данной статье были изучены социальные аспекты развития сотрудничества “семья-соседство-образовательное учреждение”.

Ключевые слова: общество, семья, соседство, школа, социальная защита, общественная деятельность, воспитание личности, здоровое поколение, гражданское общество.

INTRODUCTION

The establishment of an independent democratic state based on a market economy after our independence, the formation of a civil society with human interests, rights and freedoms, the rule of law and equality before the law for all citizens of our country, is defined as a strategic goal.

Reforms aimed at developing the activities of the Family Institute in our country, increasing spiritual and educational promotion in the neighborhoods, improving its regulatory and legal provisions and improving material and technical conditions have expanded the possibility of strengthening the participation and place of citizens' self-governing bodies in families, realizing the goal of educating a spiritually harmonious personality placed before educational processes. It is not for nothing that the Republic of Uzbekistan, in its address to the Supreme Assembly of December 29, 2020, stated that “it is necessary to further improve the local executive bodies, representative offices and the institutional framework of the neighborhood.”

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Family marriage is a great School of life, in which a couple raises each other, one learns from the other, the few in oneself notice and go to eliminate. Only a family that has withstood these shortcomings can be happy. The main goal of starting a family is to have children, to continue the continuity of generations, to work sincerely in the interests of society.

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The need arises to develop the effectiveness of the system of social protection of minor children in the family on the basis of cooperation “family-neighborhood-educational institution”. In the strategy of Action for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is established that “to educate young people who are physically healthy, mentally and mentally developed, who think independently, are loyal to the Motherland, have a strict life perspective, deepen democratic reforms and increase their social activity in the process of developing Civil Society”[1] is a priority. Of urgent importance in this regard is the enrichment of legal and regulatory provisions aimed at raising the social consciousness of minor children, the improvement of the content of social support of minor children in the family, the clarification of the cooperative functions of the public structure of The “Parent University”.

When performing these tasks, a number of important strategic goals are set before social workers. Social workers promote the involvement of people in a decision-making process aimed at changing their lives, giving them the opportunity to rely on the strengths and capabilities of people, groups, communities. Protecting the dignity of people, ensuring their safety, helping them achieve personal well-being is carried out by a social worker based on his understanding of a person in one whole with his individual, family, public characteristics, respect for his interests and needs.

The development of the national strategy of social protection in Uzbekistan and the transfer of all its functions to a single specialized institution should be developed in accordance with international standards for the social protection of children and adults. In doing so, the social protection institution effectively integrates social protection programs in various HIL.

Increasing the activity of parents or replacement persons, neighborhoods and educational institutions in foster care; the role, commitment, responsibility of parents in foster care, and assistance in strengthening interaction with children are the main tasks of the center.

When it comes to the education of young people, we have no choice but to dwell on the role and influence of the neighborhood. It is not for nothing that the “Neighborhood – both father and mother” is said. Customs and traditions inherent in our people, such as mutual affection, harmony and harmony, developed precisely in the neighborhood environment. These are important in shaping the mind-mindedness of the younger generation. So, in the education of our children, the place of the neighborhood cannot be equated with anything.

“The role of self-governing bodies in the system of civil society institutions is incomparable. After all, unlike other countries, the neighborhood Institute has been developing in our country for thousands of years as a tried and deeply rooted, social phenomenon that keeps the population together. We especially clearly see that in the context of its transition to the current market economy, it is taking the field as a guarantee to preserve the customs, traditions and values of our people, to chipsize them. The structure and function of the neighborhood varied according to the

situation, but it maintained the principle of self-government, coordinating socio-economic relations between people residing in its territory”[2, 246].

The content of preparing young people for a family based on a healthy lifestyle in the neighborhood consists in treating the family with holiness and responsibility, honoring the family, preparing young people for family life, maintaining reproductive health, maintaining life and fasting, preserving human health and forming a serious attitude to one's own health, raising gratitude, admiration, thrift, perseverance, vigor, compassion, maternal affection.

It is also important to develop forms and methods of developing the system of social protection of minor children in the family, cooperation “family – neighborhood – educational institution” in the development of the system of raising the social consciousness of minor children in the family, the development of the system of raising the social consciousness of minor children in the family.

The spiritual and moral perversion, which has become widespread all over the world in later times under the guise of “mass culture”, also poses a serious threat to the worldview of our youth. Attempts to instill alien and destructive ideas such as moral decay, violence, individualism, egocentrism into the minds of young people through the Internet are gaining momentum. We must protect our boyfriends from their influence. Therefore, in the neighborhoods, we need to organize training hours for young people, attracting specialists who can comprehensively analyze today's complex ideological processes. So that such activities reveal the essence of ideas and ideological attacks that are contrary to our national interests, our way of life. This is of particular importance in strengthening the foundations of National thinking and a healthy worldview in the hearts of our citizens.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In addition, there is now a need to further improve the monitoring of the spiritual environment in the neighborhood on a regular basis. In this way, it is possible to improve the environment in troubled families, prevent unpleasant situations that are conspicuous in the upbringing of children.

Often we do not pay attention to the problems, aspirations of our boyfriends. Or rather, we put only demand on them, and we do not count on their interests. In the words of our President, it is necessary that any parent, coach, first of all see a person in the image of each child. It would be desirable if we approached the upbringing of a child based on this simple requirement. To this end, we need to conduct social research, or rather, surveys, aimed at studying youth problems. A program of measures for the results of the study should be developed, covering tasks aimed at solving the problems of young people, realizing their dreams, ensuring their employment, the correct Organization of their free time.

CONCLUSION

As a conclusion, in improving the effectiveness of social activities in the development of family, neighborhood, school cooperation, the cooperation of the “family – neighborhood – educational institution” has a positive effect on the targeted and effective activities of the social layer in society. It is important to educate children in the spirit of an active participant in the processes of spiritual renewal of society in the family, the content of educational work carried out with parents in order to raise the legal culture of the population and improve the efficiency of a healthy lifestyle in the neighborhoods. Recommendations of citizens' assemblies: it is advisable to develop on the basis of integrative cooperation with the community council “family-neighborhood-educational institution” and the community structure “parents' university”, to

implement it through the efficient use of modern pedagogical technologies, interactive methods and information and communication technologies.

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